

STUDIES ON THE ADSORPTION OF QUININE BY DIFFERENT ADSORBENTS WITH A VIEW TO ITS EXTRACTION FROM VERY DILUTE SOLUTIONS

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The adsorption of quinine from very dilute aqueous solution (0.05-0.15%) on various adsorbents has been investigated. Of the adsorbents tried activated charcoal was found to adsorb as much as 96%, Fuller's earth 86% and kaolin 62% quinine. The results indicate a possible method of extraction of quinine from very dilute solutions by adsorbents and subsequent elution with suitable solvents.

The main source of quinine is the cinchona plant. Its bark contains 4 to 5%, while the leaves and the woody portions contain only about 0.25% and 0.45% respectively of the alkaloids on the basis of dry weight. At present quinine is extracted only from the bark, leaves and the wood being rejected. The main difficulty in its extraction from the wood is that the extract becomes very dilute with respect to the alkaloid and hence cannot be subjected effectively to the same treatment as is followed in the case of the bark. The problem therefore is to find out an easy method of concentrating the extract. One of the possible methods that occurred to us is to remove, as completely as possible, the alkaloids from the dilute solution by adsorption on a suitable adsorbent and then to obtain a concentrated solution of it by elution from the surface of the adsorbent. With this object in view, the adsorption of quinine from very dilute aqueous solutions, using a number of adsorbents, has been investigated by us.

Malquori and co-workers (*Ann. Chim. Appl.*, 1932, 22, 448) report that the Freundlich adsorption isotherm is applicable to the adsorption of quinine by a number of adsorbents, while Brintzinger and co-worker (*Kolloid Z.*, 1936, 74, 29) have found that the adsorption of the alkaloid by charcoal depends considerably on the degree of activation of the adsorbent. In this experiment we have confined ourselves to a study of the adsorption of quinine from very dilute solutions of regulated p_{H} . The results obtained are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Adsorbents

Aluminium hydroxide used in these experiments was prepared by Willstätter's method (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 149, 1117). The suspension was prepared with 2.168 g. of Al_2O_3 per 100 c.c.

Hydrated manganese dioxide was prepared as follows: To a boiling solution of 250 c.c. of 10% $MnSO_4$ (manganous sulphate) acidified by 12.5 c.c. of 20% sulphuric acid, 450 c.c. of 5% $KMnO_4$ were added. The mixture was then allowed to settle and cool, after which the clear solution was decanted off, and the precipitate of manganese dioxide washed repeatedly with distilled water until it was free of acid and the p_{H} of the wash liquid was about 6.0. The moisture content of this sample of manganese dioxide was 46.24%.

Silicic acid.—Merck's silica was used but since it was found to give a faintly alkaline reaction, it was digested with strong HCl and washed with distilled water till free from acid and p_{H} of the wash liquid was about 6.6.

Kieselghur was washed free from all electrolytes and dried in air.

Kaolin.—The sample, obtained from the market, was observed to give a faintly alkaline reaction. It was therefore digested with moderately strong HCl as in the case of silica and then washed with distilled water, till the wash liquid showed a p_H of 6.6.

Tin oxide was prepared by treating metallic tin with strong nitric acid in a fume chamber. After heating for two hours on a water-bath to drive off the nitrous fumes, it was allowed to cool. The mass was then washed with distilled water to remove the acid, dried in air and used as adsorbent.

Fuller's earth was carefully washed with distilled water till free from all electrolytes and the p_H of the wash water was about 6.6. The washed mass was then dried in air before being used for experimental purpose.

Active charcoal.—The sample of active charcoal used was from Action Moussel Co.

Estimation of Adsorption of Quinine Sulphate

A 0.15% stock solution of quinine sulphate was prepared in distilled water with the addition of a few drops of sulphuric acid to enhance its solubility in water. For each experiment an aliquot part of this solution was taken in a bottle, made up to 100 c.c. by the addition of distilled water, if necessary, and the p_H adjusted to 6.8 to 7.0 by the addition of a few drops of alkali. A known weight (usually 1 g.)* of the air-dried solid adsorbent was then added to this solution and the mixture shaken vigorously for about 20 minutes in a mechanical shaker. The content of the bottle was then filtered and the amount of the alkaloid in an aliquot portion of the filtrate was estimated in the following way.

The filtrate, thus obtained, was rendered alkaline by the addition of caustic soda and the alkaloid extracted by shaking with a mixture of 3 parts by volume of ether and one part by volume of chloroform, in the proportion (by volume) of the mixture to filtrate as 24 : 100. The chloroform-ether mixture was then withdrawn and the extraction of the filtrate repeated twice. The chloroform-ether extracts were then mixed, washed once only with a few c.c. of water and then transferred to a glass basin and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. A few drops of alcohol were then added to the residue and again evaporated to dryness. The basin was then dried in an air-oven, cooled in a desiccator and weighed. From these data the amount of quinine present in the supernatant solution after adsorption was calculated.

The quinine content of the stock solution was also determined in the same way and thus knowing the quinine concentration before and after adsorption, the amount of quinine adsorbed per gram of the adsorbent was calculated.

The results are recorded in Table I. The p_H of the quinine sulphate solution was in all cases adjusted between 6.8 and 7.0 unless otherwise stated. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature (30°). The amount of the adsorbent used was always 1 g. per 100 c.c. of the experimental solution.

*In the case of aluminium hydroxide the procedure was slightly different since this adsorbent was not used in the form of air-dried solid but as a suspension. For this reason 10 c.c. of the suspension were added to aliquot portions of the stock alkaloid solution and the total volume made up to 100 c.c. by the addition of water, after which the p_H was adjusted to 6.8—7.0

TABLE I

Conc. of quinine sulphate soln.	Amount of quinine per 100 c.c. soln. before adsorption.	Amount of quinine per 100 c.c. of filtrate after adsorption.	Wt. of quinine adsorbed.
1	2	3	4
	(a) Aluminium hydroxide*		
0.05%	0.0371 g.	0.0259 g.	0.0112 g.
0.10	0.0742	0.0557	0.0185
0.15	0.1113	0.0861	0.0252
	(b) Hydrated manganese dioxide.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0111	0.026
0.075	0.0556	0.0205	0.035
0.10	0.0742	0.0302	0.044
0.125	0.0927	0.0397	0.053
0.15	0.1113	0.0513	0.060
	(c) Silicic acid.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0241	0.013
0.10	0.0742	0.0542	0.020
0.15	0.1113	0.0843	0.027
	(d) Kieselguhr.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0201	0.017
0.075	0.0556	0.0306	0.025
0.10	0.0742	0.0422	0.032
0.125	0.0927	0.0537	0.039
0.15	0.1113	0.0663	0.045
	(e) Kieselguhr (p _H adjusted at 6.0).		
0.05	0.0371	0.0071	0.030
0.075	0.0556	0.0116	0.044
0.10	0.0742	0.0182	0.056
0.125	0.0927	0.0237	0.069
0.15	0.1113	0.0303	0.081
	(f) Kaolin.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0111	0.026
0.075	0.0556	0.0176	0.038
0.10	0.0742	0.0262	0.048
0.125	0.0927	0.0337	0.059
0.15	0.1113	0.0433	0.068
	(g) Tin oxide.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0221	0.015
0.10	0.0742	0.0462	0.028
0.15	0.1113	0.0733	0.038
	(h) Fuller's earth.		
0.05%	0.0371 g.	0.0031 g.	0.034 g.
0.075	0.0556	0.0066	0.049
0.10	0.0742	0.0132	0.061
0.125	0.0927	0.0117	0.081
0.15	0.1113	0.0153	0.096
	(i) Active charcoal.		
0.05	0.0371	0.0002	0.0369
0.075	0.0556	0.0003	0.0583
0.10	0.0742	0.0005	0.0737
0.15	0.1113	0.0006	0.1107

*Aluminium hydroxide as an adsorbent was used as a suspension containing 2.168 g. of Al_2O_3 per 100 c.c. of the suspension. Since 10 c.c. were only used per 100 c.c. of quinine solution of different concentrations the weight of the adsorbent used per 100 c.c. of quinine solution was 0.2166 g. of Al_2O_3 .

From the data recorded in Table I the adsorbing power of the substances studied appears to run in the order : charcoal > Fuller's earth > kieselguhr > kaolin > manganese dioxide > tin oxide > silicic acid.

It will also be noticed that charcoal adsorbs quinine very strongly. Experiments were therefore carried out varying the quantities of charcoal at a definite concentration of quinine sulphate. Results appear in Table II (A) from which it will be noticed that 0.6 g. of charcoal can adsorb 0.1105 g. of quinine, while 0.3 g. can adsorb as much as 0.1012 g.

TABLE II

Effect of varying the quantity of adsorbent on adsorption.

A. Quinine sulphate solution. Vol. = 100 c.c. $p_H = 6.0$.			B. Tota quinine sulphate solution. Vol. = 100 c.c. $p_H = 6.0$.	
Conc. of quinine = 0.15%. Amount of quinine per 100 c.c. before adsorption = 0.1113 g.			Conc. of alkaloid = 0.15%. Amount of alkaloid per 100 c.c. before adsorption = 0.1348 g.	
Wt. of adsorbent.	Amt. of quinine per 100 c.c. after adsorption.	Wt. of quinine adsorbed per g. of adsorbent.	Amt. of alkaloid per 100 c.c. after adsorption.	Wt. of alkaloid adsorbed per g. of adsorbent.
1.0 g.	0.0006	0.1107	0.0002	0.1346
0.8	0.0007	0.1105	0.0005	0.1343
0.6	0.0008	0.1105	0.0008	0.1340
0.4	0.0023	0.1090	0.0017	0.1331
0.3	0.0041	0.1072	0.0032	0.1316
0.2	0.0096	0.1017	0.0076	0.1262

* The p_H of water in presence of the active charcoal was found to be 5.8. The p_H of the quinine sulphate solution was therefore adjusted at 6.0 in this case. The mixture of the alkaloid solution with the adsorbent was shaken for 30 minutes instead of 20 mins. as in the case of other adsorbents.

Adsorption of Tota quinine by Charcoal.—A stock solution (0.15%) of tota quinine sulphate was prepared and experiments were carried out using varying quantities of charcoal in contact with a given concentration of tota quinine sulphate solution. The p_H was adjusted to 6.0. Results have been represented in Table II(B).

Evidently charcoal adsorbs quinine and specially tota quinine very strongly hence the possibility of elution of these alkaloids from the charcoal surface was next investigated.

Elution from Charcoal.—For this purpose two experiments were done using quinine and tota quinine. Quinine sulphate (5 g.) was dissolved in water with 10 c.c. of H_2SO_4 (10%). The volume of the solution was made up to 5 litres with water. The p_H of this quinine solution was adjusted to 6.0 and 25 g. of charcoal were added to it and the mixture was stirred using a mechanical stirrer for 2 hours. The solution was then filtered. The total volume of the filtrate was taken and its quinine content estimated. The adsorbent was weighed and half of it was taken and mixed thoroughly with 1/8th of its weight of sodium carbonate. The mixture was extracted three times in succession, using 400 c.c., 300 c.c. and 300 c.c. respectively of a benzene and amyl alcohol mixture at about 80°. From the total volume of the benzene-amyl alcohol mixture 50 c.c. were extracted with 20 c.c. of H_2SO_4 . The quinine passed into the acid solution which was separated and then treated with slight excess of alkali to liberate the alkaloid and extracted with an ether-chloroform mixture (3 parts of ether and 1 part of chloroform). The

alkaloid content of this extract was estimated in the way described before. The same procedure was followed in the case of tota quinine. The results of the two experiments are given below. It will be observed that the percentage of quinine eluted was 84% and that of tota quinine 82%.

Quinine :—Volume of 0.1% quinine sulphate solution taken=5000 c.c. which contains 5 g. of quinine sulphate or 3.71 g. of quinine.

Adsorbent used=25 g.

Amount of quinine=3.701 g.

Amount of quinine eluted from the adsorbent=3.108 g.

Hence the percentage of quinine recovered=84%.

Tota quinine :—Volume of 0.1% tota quinine sulphate solution taken=5000 c.c. which contains 5 g. tota quinine sulphate or 4.49 g. tota quinine.

Adsorbent used=25 g.

Amount of alkaloid adsorbed= $(4.49 \times 0.0075)=4.48$ g.

Amount of alkaloid eluted from the adsorbent=3.7069 g.

Hence the percentage recovered=82%.

CONCLUSION

Of the various adsorbents which have been tried, activated charcoal has been found to have the highest capacity of adsorption. As much as 96% of the quinine are adsorbed from a 0.15% solution by an amount of activated charcoal which is only twice the weight of the quinine sulphate taken. Of the remaining adsorbents, Fuller's earth and Kieselguhr also give good results, adsorbing about 86% and 62% of quinine respectively. These results indicate the possibility of utilising the phenomenon of adsorption in concentrating the cinchona alkaloids in a small volume of adsorbent from very dilute solutions, such as those likely to be obtained in the extraction of cinchona wood by treatment with acid solutions. Although active charcoal appears to be the best adsorbent, yet Fuller's earth or kaolin may be effectively used, if the adsorption is carried out in two or three successive stages. At p_H 6.0 kieselguhr also acts as a good adsorbent.

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